

SHEAR PROPERTIES OF COLLAGEN CROSSLINKED PROCINE CORNEA

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INTRODUCTION

The cornea is the outer transparent part of the eye which provides structural integrity and contributes vastly to refract light. The tissue acts as a protective layer for internal contents of the eyeball and its structural properties are important for proper vision. The optical properties of the cornea include transmission and refraction of the light. The cornea is subjected to intraocular pressure from the inside and could be subjected to external forces caused by eye rubbing, for example. The mechanical properties of the cornea are altered in several diseases such as keratoconus, which is an eye disease changing the corneal microstructure. Keratoconus affects about one in 2000 individuals and causes the cornea thins and gradually becomes a cone-like bulge. Any change in the shape of the cornea interferes with its optical properties and causes the vision to become blurry and distorted. At initial stages of the disease, eyeglasses or lenses can be used to correct for vision abnormalities. However, keratoconus is a progressive disease making the cornea to bulge more. Thus, the vision of individuals significantly decreases if no medical intervention is done.

The corneal collagen cross-linking procedure has been shown to be effective in halting or at least slowing the progression of keratoconus. In this procedure, the corneas are soaked in riboflavin solution and crosslinks are created in the corneal stroma by shining ultraviolet (UV) light. It has been shown that corneal structural properties improve because of this procedure, the progression of the disease stops, and individuals may not need corneal transplants. The strengthening effects of the collagen crosslinking treatment procedure have been commonly

investigated by performing uniaxial tensile experiments [1-2]. For example, we have shown that corneal collagen cross-linking resulted in a significant increase of tensile stress-strain response which is dependent on the hydration of the samples [3]. The primary objective of the present work was to conduct shear experiments in order to determine how corneal collagen crosslinking procedure influences shear properties of corneal samples in vitro. For this purpose, we used porcine corneas and used the Dresden crosslinking protocol to create crosslinks in vitro. We then performed oscillatory shear experiments to characterize the dynamic modulus of treated and untreated samples.

METHODS

Fresh porcine eyes were collected from an abattoir and brought to the laboratory. Corneal samples with a scleral rim were prepared after removing epithelial and endothelial layers from the samples. We divided the samples into two groups. The samples in the first group were crosslinked using photosensitizer riboflavin solution. In order to prevent excessive swelling of the specimens, we used 20% dextran in the riboflavin solution. All samples were initially soaked in the riboflavin dextran solution for 30 minutes in order to ensure proper penetration of riboflavin inside the specimens. Then, the samples were irradiated with UV light (370 nm, 3 mw/cm²) for 30 minutes. During this period, we continued instilling drops of riboflavin dextran solution every 5 minutes on the samples. Following crosslinking the samples, we used a biopsy punch to obtain corneal disks from the center of the samples.

A rheometer (DHR-2, TA instruments, Delaware) was used to perform the shear mechanical experiments. These tests were done using

the protocol that we have used before [4]. Briefly, the samples were mounted in the rheometer and the chamber was filled with PBS solution, Figure 1. In order to avoid samples to slip during the experiments, sand papers were glued to the machine. The upper geometry was then brought down and both shear frequency and strain sweep experiments were performed. The strain sweeps were performed using oscillating strains ranging from 0.01% to 10% at the frequency of 1 Hz. Furthermore, frequency sweep experiments were performed at constant oscillating strain of 0.02% and with frequencies between 0.01 Hz and 2 Hz. The storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') were calculated using the experimental measurements. The one-way ANOVA was used to compare the behavior of treated and untreated groups. The significance level of 0.05 was used in the statistical analysis.

Figure 1. A schematic plot of the dynamic torsional experimental setup. The samples were placed between the top and bottom platens and sand papers were used to avoid slippage. Furthermore, all experiments were done inside the PBS solution.

RESULTS

The storage and loss moduli of the samples in the collagen crosslinked group and the untreated group are shown in Figure 2 as function of the applied shear strain. It is seen that the shear modulus of crosslinked samples is significantly larger than the storage modulus of untreated samples. This figure also shows the range of linear viscoelasticity is almost the same in both groups, i.e. crosslinking of the samples does not have any effect on the overall shear viscoelastic response of the cornea.

DISCUSSION

The main goal of this study was to characterize the effects of corneal collagen crosslinking on shear properties of porcine corneas. The experimental measurements clearly showed that the corneal collagen crosslinking significantly increased the shear modulus of the samples. We did not see any significant difference in the characteristic curves between both groups, i.e., the linear viscoelastic region for both crosslinked and untreated groups was found to be the same. The range of linear viscoelasticity and the shear modulus of untreated samples were consistent with previous findings [4]. The possible reason for the improvement in the shear properties of the crosslinked cornea could be

the crosslinks that are formed in the collagen proteoglycan matrix. This is an important finding because although collagen fibers are important in tensile properties of the samples, shear properties of the samples are determined from the interaction of collagen fibers with the proteoglycan matrix.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: (a) storage modulus and loss modulus of crosslinked and untreated porcine corneas. The symbols denote the average of experimental measurements and the error bars indicate standard deviation.

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